

Guidelines for Using the GAIDeT Declaration Generator in the Educational Process

1 Principle of Transparency

Every written, qualification, or project work in which generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) was used must include a declaration of delegated tasks. It is recommended to create such declarations using the online [GAIDeT Declaration Generator](https://panbibliotekar.github.io/gaidet-declaration/index-uk.html). This ensures unified standards, clarity, and reliability of disclosure.

The GAIDeT Generator is freely accessible:

in Ukrainian:

<https://panbibliotekar.github.io/gaidet-declaration/index-uk.html>

in English:

<https://panbibliotekar.github.io/gaidet-declaration/index>

2 How to Use the Generator

- 1 Go to the online GAIDeT Declaration Generator.
- 2 Enter the name of the responsible author(s) of the work.
- 3 Specify the GenAI tool and its version (e.g., ChatGPT-5, Claude 3, Gemini 1.5).
- 4 Select the tasks from the GAIDeT taxonomy that were delegated to AI (e.g., text translation, style editing, code writing).
- 5 Add a brief comment if necessary (e.g., “used only for translation of selected passages”).
- 6 Click “Generate” and copy the ready-made declaration text.

3 Where to Place the Declaration

- In written or qualification works, the declaration is placed before the reference list in a separate section titled “Declaration of GenAI Use (GAIDeT)”.
- In presentations or posters, the declaration is included on the final slide or in the notes.
- In group projects, the declaration is added to the title page or appendix.

If you use this tool or the taxonomy in your research, please cite the source:

Suchikova, Y., Tsybuliak, N., & Teixeira da Silva, J. A. & Nazarovets, S. (2025). GAIDeT (Generative AI Delegation Taxonomy): A taxonomy for humans to delegate tasks to generative artificial intelligence in scientific research and publishing. *Accountability in Research*, in press. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2025.2544331>

4 Example of a Generated Declaration

GAIDeT Declaration

The authors declare the use of generative AI in the process of research and writing. According to the GAIDeT taxonomy (2025), the following tasks were delegated to AI tools under full human supervision: literature search and systematization; data analysis; translation; analysis of ethical risks. The GenAI tool used: ChatGPT-5. Responsibility for the final version of the manuscript rests entirely with the authors. AI tools are not listed as authors and bear no responsibility for the final results.

The GAIDeT Declaration Generator is a universal tool for transparent disclosure of AI's role in educational tasks and ensures compliance with the principles of academic integrity.

